

HISTORY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF MUSEUMS AND MUSEUM NETWORKS IN THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE. FERGANA MUSEUM OF PATRIOTIC SCIENCES IS AN EXAMPLE

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Annotatsiya: Barchamizga ma'lumki, mustaqillik bizga har sohada yangilanish va rivojlanish uchun muhim yo'llarni ochdi. Shu jumladan, muzeylar faoliyatida ham ko'zga ko'rinarli yangiliklar amalga oshirildi. Ushbu maqolada mustaqillik yillaridagi ayrim o'zgarishlar va muzey tarmoqlari Farg'ona o'lkashunoslik muzeyi faoliyati misolida yoritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Muzey, O'zbek muzey, IKOM, tarmoq, yo'nalish, soha, mustaqillik, Farg'ona o'lkashunoslik muzeyi, rivojlanish, noshirlik faoliyati, arxeologik izlanishlar, fond, Amir Temur, tarix, madaniyat muassasalari.

Аннотация: Как мы все знаем, независимость открыла для нас важные пути обновления и развития во всех областях. Кроме того, заметные новации были внесены в деятельность музеев. В данной статье на примере деятельности Ферганского краеведческого музея будут освещены некоторые изменения и музейные сети за годы независимости.

Ключевые слова: музей, Узбекский музей, IKOM, сеть, направление, сфера, независимость, Ферганский историко-краеведческий музей, развитие, издательская деятельность, археологические исследования, фонд, Amir Temur, история, учреждения культуры.

Annotation: As we all know, independence has opened important ways for us to update and develop in every field. In addition, notable innovations were made in the activities of museums. In this article, some changes and museum networks during the years of independence will be covered using the example of the activity of the Fergana Local History Museum.

Key words: Museum, Uzbek museum, IKOM, network, direction, field, independence, Ferghana Museum of Local History, development, publishing activity, archaeological research, fund, Amir Temur, history, cultural institutions.

In the years of independence, attention and demand for museums is increasing. This is certainly related to the social tasks of museums. To further improve the existing system of museums in the territory of Uzbekistan, to increase their role in the spiritual and moral maturity of the people, to carefully preserve, study and enrich the rich history of our nation, the steps of our independence, which are preserved in the museum funds, and the unique and rare exhibits. , to take out and promote to the world, and to use them widely in the minds of our people to strengthen national pride, independence and respect for the Motherland, feelings of loyalty. Also, providing the museums with highly qualified specialists,

strengthening the material and technical base, and creating the necessary conditions for applying the experiences of world museology are among the priority tasks. In addition, it is very important to connect museums with the Internet system and to become a scientific center. The decree of the President of our Republic "On radical improvement and improvement of the activities of museums" dated January 12, 1998 was a turning point in the life of museums and museum employees. Further improvement of the existing system of museums in the territory of our country, increasing their place in the spiritual and moral maturity of the people was set as a priority, and for this purpose, the Republican Fund "Uzbek Museum" was established. In addition, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of Uzbekistan dated March 5, 1998 "On issues of fundamental support for the activities of museums" entrusted the "Uzbek Museum" with the task of providing comprehensive support to the museums of Uzbekistan. . In this decision, the tasks of renovating the country's museums, equipping them with necessary technical and modern equipment, and providing them with funds are assigned.

Network - the activity of museums belongs to a branch of production, science, art. If we paid attention to these museum networks during the years of independence, they are developing and improving year by year after the decision of our president. Collecting and publishing activities of museums are also developing. Collecting scientific works, manuscripts found as a result of scientific ethnographic, archaeological researches and, based on these, coming out with articles of museum employees at the level of possibilities in museums. In addition, on the republican scale, it consists of covering the activities of museums in special magazines and in publishing houses, publishing brochures, posters, organizing exhibitions and covering them in methodical books, and many other works. The network is the direction of activity of these museums, i.e. scientific research, foundation work, organization of exhibitions. Scientific research studies, collecting information about the country's art, history, literature, publishing scientific publications, conducting ethnographic, archaeological scientific research. The work of the fund includes collecting and researching museum objects, organizing scientific cards, catalogs, various universal cards, permanent exhibitions, mobile exhibitions¹.

According to the mission of the museum, it is divided into scientific research, enlightenment, research and educational museums, and depending on its direction and collections, it is divided into network, local history and monumental museums. The network belongs to a branch of production, science, art in the museum (for example, history museums, zoological museums). Museums of local history comprehensively reflect the nature, history, economy, art, ethnography and other areas of a certain administrative territory².

Memorial museums are dedicated to important historical events and famous people. Today, there are branches of the Fergana Local History Museum in different districts of our region. In particular, the following:

1. "Khamza Hakimzada Niazi Museum" was opened in 1957 in the village of Shahimardan.
2. "Memorial Museum of Usman Yusupov" - opened in 1974 in the village of Kaptarkhana.
3. "Yoldosh Okhunboboyev Memorial Museum" - opened in 1964 in the city of Margilon.
4. "Museum of History of Uzbekistan District" in Yaipan was opened in 1984.
5. "Museum of Literature and Art" was opened in 1989 in the city of Margilan.

¹ I. Sodikova "Madaniy yodgorliklar hazinasi" T."Fan" 1981 y

² Рекомендации по учету и хранению ценностей в музеях система.-Москва.1977.

6. "Ziyovutdin Khaziniy Uy Museum" in Uchkoprik District was opened in 1997.

7. "Museum of History" of Altiariq district was opened in 2000³.

If we look at the activities of these industries, we can see that the decree of the President, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers, and the decision of the regional government have motivated the improvement, improvement and development of these industries. The existence of museums in cultural and public educational institutions is considered to be the center of culture that plays an important role in educating young people in the spirit of patriotism. These include museums of fame, history of the country, antiques of labor veterans, history of great figures, and antiques that tell the story of the country's history. Today, there are more than 1,200 museums in the territory of our country under various institutions, enterprises, construction organizations, rural collective management farms, in city, district, regional centers, and in the public education system, the largest of which are located in the capital. At the same time, there are home museums of dozens of writers, poets, artists, scientists and famous artists. These museums are spiritual centers that tell the long history of our nation, echoing from the museum, and are great steps in developing national ideology and thinking, raising national pride and pride among young people.

Museums that reflect the history of the formation of each nation and related political processes are national museums. Ichan Castle in Khorezm, Bukhara Arch are examples of national museums. On October 18, 1996, in the heart of ancient Tashkent, the capital of our country, the recitation of the Qur'an spread far and wide. In memory of our great grandfather, the great statesman and invincible commander Amir Temur, a unique and miraculous example of Eastern national architecture was built, and the grand opening of the State Museum of the History of the Timurids increased attention to the study of the history of our country. In the speech of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I. Karimov at the opening ceremony of the museum, it is said: "After the independence of our country, the person of Amir Temur became the symbol of the homeland and the nation again. He noted that he is becoming more and more and continues his opinion and says, "Great personalities are created by history."⁴

The State Museum of the History of the Timurids is an architecturally perfect and magnificent building. First of all, this is worthy of the present enthusiasm, worldly reputation and genius of our ancestors, and secondly, it testifies to the creative power, incomparable talent and limitless imagination of the Timurid generation. Moreover, its importance is very great for better study of Timur and the state of the Timurids, its implementation in life, and the illumination of the true history of our national history. Today, this museum has become a scientific center. The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers dated March 5, 1998 entrusted the "Uzbek Museum" foundation with the task of providing comprehensive support to the museums of Uzbekistan, taking into account the fact that the Public Council of Museums of Uzbekistan is a member of the International Council of Museums ICOM⁵.

Uzbek museums work in cooperation with many prominent countries of the world, namely museums of England, America, Italy, France, Germany, guidebooks, booklets and catalogs are

³ O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 1998-yil 10-yanvardagi "O'zbekiston muzeylari ishini takomillashtirish va rivojlantirish to'g'risida"gi qarori.

⁴ I. A. Karimov "Tarixiy xotirasiz kelajak yuk" T.1998 y.

⁵ "Moziydan sado" jurnali, 2019-yil 4-soni.

published and displayed. exhibitions are being organized. Our Ferghana Museum of Local History cooperates with many countries, including conducting scientific research on the ancient history of Ferghana in cooperation with the Japanese Museum of Ethnography. Museum employees are invited to Japan to study at the scientific center. In addition, permanent relations are maintained with the Russian State Hermitage, the Russian State Museum of Ethnography in St. Petersburg, the Institute of Archeology of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, and the Museums of the History of the Peoples of Uzbekistan.

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